

Literature analysis of how well rDNA sequence perform at delineating dinoflagellate species

R. Wayne Litaker^{1*}, Brittany M. Ott^{2*}, William C. Holland³, Charles F. Delwiche⁴

¹ CSS, Inc. under Contract to National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration Beaufort, NC, U.S.A.; ² Joint Institute for Food Safety and Applied Nutrition (JIFSAN), University of Maryland, College Park, MD, U.S.A.; ³ National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, National Ocean Service, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science, Beaufort Laboratory, Beaufort, NC, U.S.A.; ⁴ Cell Biology and Molecular Genetics, University of Maryland, College Park, MD, U.S.A.

*corresponding author's emails: wayne.r.litaker@noaa.gov, brittany.ott@fda.hhs.gov

Abstract

Dinoflagellate harmful algal bloom species are traditionally defined using morphological characters. Molecular evidence, however, sometimes indicates that morphospecies differ from biological species. This has led to a reliance on molecular characteristics, primarily rDNA-based phylogenies, along with morphology, as a basis for defining new species. This approach assumes that divergence in rDNA or other selected genes consistently parallels speciation events, but this has not been systematically tested. Consequently, this study was undertaken to assess how often rDNA molecular phylogenies succeeded or failed to delineate dinoflagellate species. Specifically, SSU, D1-D3 LSU and ITS/5.8S phylogenies presented in 473 publications were reviewed to determine how well the rDNA phylogenies discriminated dinoflagellate species, including those in known HAB genera. A total of 863 described species representing 232 genera were assessed. Results showed the ITS/5.8S and D1-D3 LSU rDNA phylogenies (~1,850-2,500 bp), in combination, can simultaneously (a) identifying 97% of all dinoflagellate species and (b) provide unique sequences useful for developing species-specific, quantitative molecular assays. Genera where species are well resolved using the ITS/5.8S plus D1-D3 genes include *Alexandrium*, *Ostreopsis* and *Gambierdiscus*. Based on the review of the publications, it was also possible to develop a system for determining how much weight to assign morphological versus molecular characters when describing new species. Utilizing this system can accelerate the description of new dinoflagellate HAB species and the subsequent assessment of their relative toxicities.

Keywords: 5.8S, *Alexandrium*, *Gambierdiscus*, ITS, large and small subunit, ribosomal DNA, *Ostreopsis*, phylogeny

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7035075>

Introduction

Significant efforts are underway to identify and describe new species in various dinoflagellate harmful algal bloom (HAB) genera. These efforts have been driven to some extent by the documented co-occurrence of species with nearly identical morphologies but whose toxicity is significantly different. Accurately determining risk in these situations requires that all the co-existing species have been identified, their toxicity evaluated, and molecular or morphological methods developed to accurately determine species composition.

Historically, dinoflagellate species have been described based upon morphological differences in the overall size and shape of the cell, the arrangement, size, and shape of thecal plates covering the cell surface, or internal structural differences (Fensome *et al.*, 1999). Descriptions based solely on morphology, however, have sometimes proven inadequate for identifying species with overlapping morphologies. Consequently, over the past few decades more reliance has been placed on using molecular characters, particularly phylogenetic analyses of rDNA sequences in conjunction with morphology to describe new species. Specifically, the rDNA data are thought to strongly support description of a new species when all the sequences from the putative new species (i.e. obtained from either culture isolates or field-collected cells) included in a phylogenetic analysis fall into a distinct, well-defined clade. How often rDNA sequences, like morphological characters, fail to delineate species, however, has not been systematically examined. To quantify the actual success or failure rate, we reviewed 473 articles containing phylogenies based on

either the SSU, ITS/5.8S or the D1-D3 LSU rDNA domains to determine how well these phylogenies supported currently described species, including those belonging to HAB genera.

Methods and Results

Articles containing relevant rDNA phylogenies were identified using Web of Science, Google searches, or manuscript reference sections. The nomenclatural changes for the various species occurring since those species were first described were determined using AlgaeBase. Tracking these nomenclatural changes was key to resolving instances where sequences ascribed to different species but placed in a single, distinct clade were either (a) actually derived from truly different species (i.e. the rDNA failed to distinguish species) or (b) were sequences from the same species which had different species names depending on when they were entered into GenBank.

The actual determination of whether the rDNA truly delineated (resolved) species was straightforward in most cases, but nuanced in some. Factors complicating this determination included: (a) whether a single sequence or multiple sequences from a given species were included in the phylogeny (more sequences = greater resolution), and (b) whether all the sequences falling into a given clade were properly identified as noted above. Accordingly, species in the various rDNA phylogenies were classified as follows:

- Yes (=Y), cases where two or more sequences originating from a described species form a distinct clade in the rDNA

- phylogeny – i.e. phylogeny completely supports the previously described species.
- Yes provisionally (=YP), same as Y except the species-specific clade is represented by only a single rDNA sequence.
 - Yes, but ambiguous (=YA), indicates two or more sequences attributed to different species form a distinct clade in the rDNA phylogeny and where there is some suggestive, but not definitive, morphological or taxonomic information indicating the sequences are actually from the same rather than different species.
 - No (=N) denotes cases where sequences from different known morphologically distinct species are identical and fall into the same clade – i.e. rDNA phylogenies are incapable of resolving certain morphologically well-defined species.
 - No, but ambiguous (=NA), represents a version of the previous N designation where there is less definitive, but still strong, morphological evidence are indeed distinct species.

Because the species included in the various phylogenies were inconsistent, it was possible for separate phylogenies to indicate a different classification for a given species. For example, a species might be assigned as Y in one study and YP in another, or N versus NA, etc. These differing assignments have to be considered when deciding on how well the rDNA phylogenetic data are able to distinguish species. This was accomplished as follows.

- Species receiving Y, YP or Y/YP designations were assigned to the “resolved” category, i.e. the rDNA phylogeny fully supports the current species description.
- Those with N, NA, N/NA, N/YA, or

N/Y designations were classified as “not resolved”, i.e. the rDNA phylogeny failed to delineate what are clearly distinct species.

- Species with YA, Y/YA or YP/YA designations were classified as “ambiguous”, i.e. the existing data are insufficient to resolve whether the rDNA phylogenies do or do not support the currently described species.

Overall, the SSU and D1-D3 sequences have similar success at delineating > 93% of the dinoflagellate species surveyed, with the ITS/5.8S region capable of resolving > 97% of species (Fig. 1). These data indicate the ITS/5.8S region alone could distinguish most species. However, addition of the D1-D3 further strengthens resolution of the identified species boundaries. Also, the D1-D3 region exhibits a greater sequence variation per base pair compared to the SSU. Consequently, if both the D1-D3 and ITS/5.8S regions are sequenced, it facilitates subsequent identification of unique sequences that can be used to develop quantitative, species-specific molecular assays. In contrast, the SSU region, which would provide equal resolution of species boundaries provides fewer unique site for probe development and is about 600 bp longer to sequence. For this reason, the use of ITS/5.8S in combination with D1-D3 is recommended over ITS/5.8S plus the SSU as the minimum standard for resolving species. If sequencing resources allow, adding the SSU and D8-D10 LSU sequence data to the phylogenies will only further strengthen confidence in the identified species boundaries (Gottschling *et al.*, 2020).

Though successful most of the time, the literature review revealed the divergence in

the rDNA genes for about 3% of the species was insufficient to distinguish species. This includes one or more species in the following genera: *Amphidinium*, *Apocalathium*, *Archaeoperidinium*, *Biecheleria*, *Centrodinium*, *Ceratocorys*, *Dinophysis*,

previously described species, (b) failed to resolve previously described, morphologically well-defined species, or (c) gave ambiguous results due to the data being insufficient to classify the species as either resolved or not resolved. These data represent the summarized results from reviewing phylogenies from the 473 publications reviewed. N = total number of described species found in phylogenies for the particular rDNA gene segment listed in each panel.

Fig. 1. Pie charts showing the percent of species for which the D1-D3 domains of LSU, SSU, and ITS/5.8S rDNA phylogenies either (a) resolved (confirmed)

Gonyaulax, *Gymnodinium*, *Prorocentrum*, *Scrippsiella*, and *Syltrodinium*. HAB genera where species were consistently resolved include *Alexandrium*, *Gambierdiscus* and *Ostreopsis*.

A more detailed examination of the literature survey results revealed there were five discernible patterns with regard to how well the morphological and molecular data either succeeded or failed to delineate species. The patterns are described below and can be used in helping guide the identification and description of new dinoflagellate species.

Pattern 1 includes those species which are so morphologically distinct they are reliably identified based on morphology alone. In these instances, we advocate the species description also include the corresponding ITS/5.8S and D1-D3 data to help in tracing any future taxonomic changes to assist in distinguishing closely related species that might be discovered in the future, and to facilitate linkage with environmental molecular studies.

Pattern 2 represents instances where the species in question exhibit non-overlapping morphologies consistent with their being distinct species, but whose rDNA sequences are identical. About 3% of the species

examined in the survey fell in this category. These species likely represent recently diverged species whose rDNA sequences have not had sufficient time to diverge (Hickerson *et al.*, 2006), but could also reflect uncharacterized developmental variation. This represents the most difficult case to evaluate. It is recommended that prior to describing such a species, a multigene phylogenetic study be conducted to test the hypothesis that the morphotypes are distinct species. If supporting evidence is found, then the species description would be based on morphology and the multigene phylogeny. If no multigene phylogenetic differences exist, but other compelling data such as one species living exclusively in freshwater habitats and the other in saltwater environments, those data can be used as a basis for the species description (Logares *et al.*, 2007; Čalasan *et al.*, 2019). Such descriptions should include the ITS/ 5.8S and D1-D3 sequence data from the new species along with a detailed description of the other morphologically distinct species sharing the same rDNA ribotype. If no molecular data support the distinction but there is a compelling reason to name a new species, the best available option is to base the species description solely on morphology.

A good example of where morphologically distinct species with identical rDNA sequences occur is in the genus *Dinophysis*. Many of the species such as *D. acuta*, *D. caudata*, *D. dens*, *D. forti* and *D. norvegica* are genetically and morphologically distinct and represent species consistent with pattern 1. In contrast, many of the smaller celled species such as *D. acuminata*, *D. ovum*, *D. okamurai*, *D. pavillardii*, *D. recurva* and *D. sacculus* exhibit indistinguishable ITS and D1-D3

rDNA sequences (Qui *et al.*, 2011; Rodríguez *et al.*, 2012; Wolny *et al.*, 2020). These latter species should be considered valid species until additional definitive morphological or other data prove otherwise.

Pattern 3 includes species such as those in the genus *Gambierdiscus* which are morphologically difficult to distinguish but whose ITS/5.8S and D1-D3 phylogenies clearly show that they are distinct species. In this case, species can be described based solely on the rDNA phylogenetic data. This category also includes cryptic species which are truly morphologically indistinguishable. It can be reasonably claimed that all the species fitting this pattern be described as separate species. We argue, however, that in the case of the cryptic species, it is more prudent to assign each putative species a unique ribotype designation until some toxicological or other function justifies a formal description. This would avoid a proliferation of molecularly distinct, but morphologically identical species whose function is unknown.

Pattern 4 represents a small number of species where the existing morphological and molecular data provide contradictory or difficult to reconcile results such as in the case of *Peridinium cinctum* (López *et al.*, 2018). In these cases, additional morphological or phylogenetic studies are required prior to undertaking species descriptions.

Pattern 5 is included for completeness and represents cases where neither the morphological or molecular data indicate species level differences. Here, any isolates in question would be considered as belonging to the same species.

Finally, and most importantly, it should be noted that all species descriptions must contain a complete, detailed morphological description. No matter how compelling the molecular data, accurate morphological descriptions are indispensable. This is true even for cases such as cryptic species where no morphological distinctions exist. Having these data available is critical if ecologists, toxicologists and other researchers are to accurately assess the species they are working with.

The ITS/5.8S and D1-D3LSU rDNA genes in combination accurately delineate 97% of described dinoflagellate species studied to date, including most HAB species. Following the guidelines provided above, it should be possible to more effectively and systematically utilize combined morphological and molecular data to identify and describe new species. These guidelines include how to recognize and describe those morphologically distinct species, but whose rDNA sequences are indistinguishable.

In the future, multigene approaches will undoubtedly become more streamlined and affordable. The resulting phylogenies will provide an enhanced ability to resolve species boundaries. They will also provide more accurate assessment of the phylogenetic relationships among species than can be achieved with rDNA sequences alone (Leliaert *et al.*, 2014). However, at present, multigene approaches are still relatively expensive, and neither standardized nor (at present) particularly effective at distinguishing morphospecies with indistinguishable rDNAs (Kretzschmar *et al.*, 2019). Until these methods are further refined, results of this study recommend a reliance on the ITS/5.8S

and D1-D3 rDNA sequences as a key basis for defining most dinoflagellate species.

Acknowledgements. This work was supported by NSF Grant #DEB1541529 to CFD and NOAA, National Ocean Service, National Centers for Coastal Ocean Science program funds to WL and CH.

References

- Čalasan, A.Ž., Kretschmann, J., Gottschling M. (2019). *Environ. Microbiol.* 21, 4125-4135.
- Fensome, R., Saldarriaga, J., Taylor, F. (1999). *GRANA* 38, 66-80.
- Gottschling, M., Chacón, J., Žerdoner Čalasan, A., *et al.*, (2020). *Freshw. Biol.* 65, 193-208.
- Hickerson, M., Stahl, E., Lessios H. (2006) *Evolution* 60, 2435-2453.
- Kretzschmar, A.L., Larsson, M.E., Hoppenrath, M., *et al.*, (2019). *Protist* 170, 125699.
- Leliaert, F., Verbruggen, H., Vanormelingen, P., *et al.*, (2014). *Eur. J. Phycol.* 49, 179-196.
- López, A.I., Kretschmann, J., Čalasan, A.Ž., Gottschling, M. (2018). *Eur. J. Phycol.* 53, 156-165.
- Qiu, D., Huang, L., Liu, S. *et al.*, (2011). *PLoS One* 6, e29398.
- Rodríguez, F., Escalera, L., Reguera, B., *et al.*, (2012). *Harmful Algae* 13, 26-33.

Taylor, F.J.R. (1987). The Biology of
Dinoflagellates. 24-91 Blackwell Scientific,
Oxford.

